

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B296
Date: 21 June 2007
Take Off 09:59:34
Landing: 14:49:23
Flight Time 4h 49m 49s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Niamey - Nouakchott

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Mission Scientist 2	Jim Haywood	Met Office
7	Mission Scientist 1	Ben Johnson	Met Office
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
11	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
12	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
13	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	Leeds University
14	CCM2	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
15	Ballast	Jamie Trembath	FAAM

Flight Track:

B296 Track 21-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B296

Date: 21 Jun 2007

Project: GERBIL

Location: Niamey to Nouakchott over desert areas.

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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092935		inu	0.74 kft	110	to nav
092944		gin	0.74 kft	110	on
093023		cgps	0.74 kft	110	b296cgps.log
095524		pirouette	0.73 kft	086	
095739		pirouette	0.72 kft	087	090M start
095934		T/O	0.73 kft	267	Niamey
095952	102313	Profile 1	0.97 - 22.0 kft	265	start as t/o
100102		heimann	1.8 kft	270	open
100129		psap	2.2 kft	272	flow on @ t/o
100148		TW	2.4 kft	273	on
100220		Video	2.8 kft	272	#1 ffc, #2 dfc
102313	120105	Run 1	22.0 kft	301	
103223		bbr	22.0 kft	294	retract
103431		heimann	22.0 kft	293	cal 13
103542		JW	22.0 kft	293	on & zero
103813		Sonde 1	22.0 kft	294	
110936		Sonde 2	22.0 kft	256	
113843		Sonde 3	22.0 kft	255	
115855		sonde 4	22.0 kft	253	
120121	121730	Profile 2	21.4 - 3.3 kft	253	
120205		!	20.1 kft	251	2000ft min initial
120227		bbr	19.4 kft	250	extend
120334		!	18.1 kft	249	fl 190 1000ft min
121529		psap	5.5 kft	259	flow off
121731	122158	Run 2.1	3.3 kft	256	
121746		psap	3.3 kft	257	flow on
121800		bbr	3.3 kft	258	retract
122158	122617	Profile 3	3.3 - 7.5 kft	278	
122220		psap	3.4 kft	280	flow off
122233		bbr	3.7 kft	281	extend
122528		psap	6.8 kft	291	flow on
122618	122742	Run 3.1	7.5 kft	290	
122648		bbr	7.5 kft	290	retract
122803	122922	Orbit 1	7.5 kft	003	005M
123002	123126	Orbit 2	7.6 - 7.5 kft	067	090M
123204	123320	Orbit 3	7.5 kft	159	160M
123507	124239	Profile 4	7.5 - 15.0 kft	303	
124239	124636	Profile 5	15.0 - 12.0 kft	287	
124636	130310	Run 4.1	12.0 kft	287	
130310	130939	Profile 6	12.0 - 18.0 kft	286	
130940	131152	Run 5.1	18.0 kft	283	
131152	131353	Profile 7	18.0 - 16.0 kft	283	
131353	133025	Run 6.1	16.0 kft	283	
131844		psap	16.0 kft	284	filter change 13:17:00
133025	133639	Profile 8	16.0 - 22.0 kft	288	
133211		bbr	17.5 kft	287	extend
133639	140134	Run 7.1	22.0 kft	337	
133657		Sonde 5	22.0 kft	337	
133743		bbr	22.0 kft	343	retract
134046		video	22.0 kft	348	#3 & #4 end, #5ffc, #6dfc started
140134	142219	Profile 9	22.0 - 0.13 kft	345	
140205		heimann	21.6 kft	346	cal 14
140215		bbr	21.4 kft	347	extend
142219	143539	Run 8.1	0.13 - 0.16 kft	032	
142323		heimann	0.14 kft	026	cal 11
142331		bbr	0.14 kft	026	retract
144923		Land	0.08 kft	034	Nouakchott
145240	145424	pirouette	0.10 kft	036	045M

B296 Track 21-JUN-07

FAAM sortie brief

GERBILS

Flight No: 296

21st June 2007

Objectives

1. Measure the radiative effect of Saharan dust over the desert.
2. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust.

Location

From Niamey to Nouakchott over dessert areas.

Desired weather

High dust loadings. Clear skies.

Special requirements

Dropsondes.

Instruments of importance

Nephelometers (wet and dry)

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

AIRES

Flight pattern

1. Take off from Niamey at 10Z (11L).
2. Profile climb to above dust layer at 1000ft/min [25mins, T=25mins].
3. SLR at range height towards point KONAD [20mins, T=55mins].
4. Drop a sonde 15mins after start of SLR.
5. At point A (estimated to be between ETRUL and FIR) descend to to FL160 or level within significant dust (max rate above dust, 1000ft/min in dust) [5mins, T=60mins].
6. SLR for 15mins within top part of dust layer [15mins, T=75mins].
7. Profile ascent to range altitude (1000ft/min in dust then max ascent rate once above dust) [5mins, T=80mins].
8. Continue SLR at range altitude, drop sonde 15mins after start of run and every 30mins thereafter [60mins, T=140mins].
9. Profile down to MPA at max descent rate above dust, then 1000ft/min in dust layer aiming to be 25miles east of point B (estimated to be KONAD ~18N, 10W) [20mins, T=160mins].
10. SLR at MPA for 15mins. SWS to increment through a range of angles. AIRES to point up [15mins, T=175mins].
11. Reciprocal turn and SLR at MPA for 12mins. SWS and AIRES to swap from up to down [15mins, T=190mins].
12. Stack of two 12min SLRs within the dust layer (heights to be determined by mission scientist, e.g. FL075, FL150). Profiles inbetween at 1000ft/min and staggered to enable SLRs to be above each other [40mins, T=230mins].

Mission scientist debrief

B296 – GERBILS flight Niamey to Nouakchott

Location

Southerly route via Southern Mali, Senegal and southern Mauritania, plus ocean areas just off Nouakchott.

Mission aims

Radiative effect of Saharan dust over North Africa and over the ocean. Insitu sampling of Saharan dust aerosol.

Weather

Mostly clear skies except for some mid and high level cloud near Niamey and some low-level stratocumulus during low-level work over eastern Senegal.

Flight plans

Pirouettes done at both ends. At Niamey there were a few blobs of altocumulus about that might have affected the BBRs a little bit, although there was not obvious interference when looking at the irradiances as a function of time before or after the manouvers. Take off at 10Z followed by a profile climb to FL220 heading towards the NE corner of Burkina Faso. A long high level run with 4 sondes dropped along the way. Profile descent was made finishing in the western corner of Mali. Very high dust concentrations (Nephelometer was several hundred $\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, even increased to 1200 in a narrow layer around FL120). There was some stratocumulus around 6000ft in a moist BL, below residual continental BLs. Dust aerosol top was around FL200 and reduced markedly around 7000ft. Profile went to 3,300ft. A short run at that level was aborted due to cloud above. Then climb to FL075 and some orbits at that level. Unfortunately the solar zenith angle was too low for these to be useful (11 degrees). Profile climb to FL150 then back down to FL120 followed by a run at FL120 for 15mins. Then climb to FL180 and drop back to FL160 for a run at FL160 for 15-20mins. Nephelometer was 200-500 $\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ along these runs (thick aerosol). Climb to FL220 for a run above dust (dust top at FL200). A profile descent was made to the surface over the ocean 100 miles south of Nouakchott. Then a run at 100ft was made before landing at Nouakchott. SST was 24C, sea state calm though some evidence from SID of spherical aerosols and slightly higher concentrations trapped in the marine BL that was 2000ft deep (i.e. sea salt). There was no cloud visible for the low-level run. Pirouette after landing had no cloud visible but quite hazy (7km visibility reported by airport).

Summary

Good insitu sampling of high concentrations of dust and nice profiles through a large dust storm that was plunging down toward Senegal. Good radiation measurements at high level over land and low-level over the ocean.

13. Profile ascent to a level above dust at 1000ft/min, drop one sonde on reaching top of profile [5mins, T=235mins].
14. SLR towards Nouakchot, maybe drop another sonde enroute [30mins, T=265mins].
15. Profile descent into Nouakchott [20mins, T=285mins = 4:45].
16. Land Nouakchot.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.296** Date **21/6/07** Name **Pan Johnson** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					little bit of altocumulus (1/8) but not obscuring sun. visibility reasonable (not particularly dusty)
095524 -095739	T10 P1	(700Fe)			Pirouette: ABRs don't show any obvious sign of cloud diffuse
095936	T10		270	NIAMEY	
095936	P1	sfc - FL220	270 330	NIAMEY to NE tip of backing fog	
100500 095936					little bit of cirrus about or maybe its altocumulus
1010					PRASP behaving SID seeing spherical particles
102000	P1	FL170	300	14.5N 1.1E	rust top at FL170
102313	End				CO quite high (430 ppbv)
102313	R1.1	FL220			Turnrol ~ 4km x 10 ⁻⁶ ~ 0.2
103813	Dropsonde	FL220	255	15.2N 0.4W	Dropsonde 1 successful
112000					Rust below increasing, visibility and SWS increasing return
110936	Dropsonde	"	240	14.7N 3.3W	Dropsonde 2 successful except data
102000 -1100		"			PRASP Flow/pump failure at some point and for remainder of flight.
113813	Dropsonde	"	250	13.7N 5.8W	Dropsonde 3 successful
114500					Can't see surface at all upwelling SW ~ 300 W.m ⁻²

Downwelling SW ~ 1200 W.m⁻²

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...296...** Date **21/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120121	P2	FL220	255	132N 78W	
		FL200			62cm dropped from 80 to 40 as we entered dust layer at FL200
115855	Drop FL220	FL220	13.3W	Alt (MFL) 20	
					Can't see the ground until 10,000 ft
					Small cu with tops at FL6500 base at FL4500
121731	End P2	FL033	270	12.75N	very little aerosol near surface
121731	P2.1	"	285	91W	Too much cloud so abort
122158	P3	FL033			climb to FL075
122617	End	FL075			Solar Zenith angle = 11°
122803	O1	FL075			Orbits (bit useless)
123204	O2	"			(woops!)
13507	O3	"			

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.296** Date **21/6/07** Name **Ben Johnson** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123507	P4	FL075			⊙ Dust has v. different vertical profile here
124239	End	FL150			
124239	P5	FL150			
124636	End	FL120			
124636	R4.1	FL120	13.1M 10.7W	287	
130310	End	"			
130310	P6	FL120			
130939	P6	FL150			
130940	R7	FL180			
131152	P7	FL180			250 x 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
131353	End	FL160			Neph
1259					ARIES crashed
13000					
13000					Neph quite high 200-500 x 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
133025	P8	FL160			
133639	End	FL220			Dust top at FL200
133657	Drops	FL220			Drop send 5
1340					Still very thick dust below can only just see the surface
140134	P9	FL220	16.2W 15.4W		
1400		FL220			Dust less thick over here Neph only up to 50-150 on this profile, still bit crusty but not that ^{as} much as before.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B296

Date : 21/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air. Data incorrect.
O₃	None
NO_x	None
TDLAS	None

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 296

Date: 21/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:04:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:59:54																Start P1 from Takeoff	
10:01:18	360	0.09	6	10	1											FL020	
10:02:41	270	0.09		10	1											FL030	
10:03:35	370	0.09		30	3											FL040	
10:04:55	180	0.11	7	20	3											FL050	
10:06:01	115	0.13		20	5											FL060	
10:06:55	85	0.12		20	3											FL070	
10:07:55	80	0.12		15	3											FL080	
10:08:59	80	0.12	8	15	2											FL090	
10:10:00	65	0.11		10	3											FL100	
10:11:05	55	0.11		10	2											FL110	
10:12:07	40	0.10		5	2											FL120	
10:13:18	10	0.11	9	5	2											FL130	
10:14:28	25	0.11		5	2											FL140	
10:15:33	15	0.11		5	1											FL150	
10:16:40	20	0.11		5	1											FL160	
10:17:48	10	0.10		3	1											FL170	
10:18:59	6	0.16		3	1											FL180	
10:20:09	5	0.12		5	1											FL190	
10:21:10	5	0.12		2												FL200	
10:22:10	2	0.08		1												FL210	
10:23:09																End of P1 & Start Run 1 @ FL220	
10:25:00	5	0.13		1													
10:30:00	Noise			1													
10:35:00	2	0.12															
10:40:00	Noise			1													
10:45:00	2	0.11	10	1													
10:50:00	2	0.11		1													
10:55:00	1	0.11		1													
11:00:00	Motor	Failed															
11:05:00				1													
11:10:00				1													
11:15:00				1													
11:20:00				1	1												
11:25:00			11	1	1												
11:30:00				1													
11:35:00				1													
11:40:00				1													
11:45:00				1													
11:50:00				1													
11:55:00				1													
11:59:16																End of Run 1	
12:01:00																Start P2 from FL220	
12:02:10				30	10											FL200	
12:03:37				80	10											FL180	
12:04:35				90	10											FL170	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 296

Date: 21/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:04:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:05:32			12	80	10											FL160	
12:06:30				70	10											FL150	
12:07:33				70	10											FL140	
12:08:38			13	200	40											FL130	
12:09:40			17	900	90											FL120	
12:10:14			19	700	60											FL110	
12:11:12			21	300	30											FL100	
12:12:06			22	100	10											FL090	
12:13:02				110	30											FL080	
12:14:00			23	110	30											FL070	
12:15:07			29	80	20											FL060	
12:15:55			61	70	10											FL050	
12:16:44				60	10											FL040	
12:17:26																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2.1 @ 1000' agl	
12:18:00				50	10	1	200								Dust		
12:20:00			62	40	10												
12:21:50																End of Run 2.1 & start P3	
12:22:54			64	50	10											FL040	
12:23:50			200	1000	1000											FL050	
12:24:50			370	1000	1000											FL060	
12:26:05																End of P3 & Start Run 3.1 @ FL075	
12:27:00			386	90	10												
12:28:06																End of Run 3.1 & Start Orbits	
12:33:16																End of Orbits	
12:35:08			392	90	10											Start P4.1 from FL075	
12:36:44				30	10											FL090	
12:37:47			393	60	10											FL100	
12:38:55			394	100	10											FL110	
12:39:58				100	10											FL120	
12:41:00			395	90	10											FL130	
12:41:49				100	10											FL140	
12:42:33			396	100	10											End of P4 & Start P5 FL150	
12:43:50				100	8											FL140	
12:45:00				90	10											FL130	
12:46:28																End of P5 & Start Run 4.1 @ FL120	
12:47:00			397	70	10												
12:49:00				60	10												
12:51:00				90	10												
12:53:00			398	90	10												
12:55:00			399	100	10												
12:57:00			400	100	10												
13:02:50																End of Run 4.1 Start P6	
13:04:20			405	150	20											FL130	
13:05:15			406	150	30											FL140	
13:06:11			407	150	20											FL150	
13:07:14				150	25											FL160	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 296

Date: 21/06/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:04:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:08:15			408	10	10											FL170	
13:09:25																End of P6 & Start Run 5.1 @ FL180	
13:10:00			409	120	10												
13:11:39																End of Run 5.1 & Start P7 from FL180	
13:12:45			410	150	20											FL170	
13:13:48																End of P7 & Start Run 6.1 @ FL160	
13:14:00			411	200	30												
13:16:00			412	200	30												
13:18:00			415	200	20												
13:20:00			418	150	20												
13:22:00			420	150	20												
13:24:00			422	100	20												
13:26:00			424	100	10												
13:28:00			426	100	10												
13:30:00			428	100	10												
13:30:20																End of Run 6.1 & Start P8	
13:31:27			429	120	10											FL170	
13:32:45			431	120	10											FL180	
13:33:44			432	100	8											FL190	
13:34:39				1	1											FL200	
13:35:38				1												FL210	
13:36:37				1	1											End of P8 & Start Run 7.1 @ FL220	
13:37:00				1	1												
13:40:00			432	1	1												
13:45:00				2	1												
13:50:00				2	1												
13:55:00				2	1												
14:00:00			433	2													
14:01:36																End of Run 7.1 & Start P9	
14:02:38				2	1											FL210	
14:03:43				5	1											FL200	
14:04:25				10	1											FL190	
14:05:18				10	1											FL180	
14:05:53				20	1											FL170	
14:06:42				90	1											FL160	
14:07:37				80	5											FL150	
14:08:29				70	6											FL140	
14:09:30				60	8											FL130	
14:10:11				60	7											FL120	
14:10:59				60	7											FL110	
14:11:48				50	2											FL100	
14:12:38				50	5											FL090	
14:13:29				40	5											FL080	
14:14:16				40	5											FL070	
14:15:03				40	3											FL060	
14:16:07				40	3											FL050	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 296

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:17:10			436	50	10											FL040	
14:18:10			437	50	10											FL030	
14:19:30			438	50	8											FL020	
14:20:29			439	30	3											FL010	
14:22:14																End of P9 & Start Run 8.1 @ 100'	
14:23:00			440	70	10												
14:25:00				80	10												
14:27:00			441	70	10												
14:29:00				60	3												
14:31:00			442	30	3												
14:33:00				30	5												
14:35:00			443	40	3												
14:35:43																End of Run 8.1	
PCASP failed after First Profile PCASP2 Flowrate = 1CC/sec FFSSP signal offset changed as required																	

B296_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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08:57:57.57 --- - - - -
08:57:57.57 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:57:57.57 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period / tVIS/ tNIR /
                                Comment +++
08:57:57.57 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B296
08:57:57.57 --- - - - -
09:03:49.12 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:03:51.46 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:03:54.13 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:04:09.28 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:04:13.59 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:04:20.43 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:04:21.43 SWS - - - - Idling
09:04:25.48 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:04:26.27 USH - - - - Idling
09:04:30.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:04:31.26 LSH - - - - Idling
09:04:34.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:04:34.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:04:34.20 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:04:43.29 SWS - - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
09:04:46.09 SWS - - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
09:04:49.81 USH - - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
09:04:53.13 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
09:04:56.00 LSH - - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
09:04:59.46 LSH - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
09:05:02.60 LSH - - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
09:05:08.40 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:05:08.40 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:05:08.58 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:05:12.36 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:05:14.05 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:05:16.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:05:19.89 SWS - - - - Idling
09:05:22.09 USH - - - - Idling
09:05:24.67 LSH - - - - Idling
09:05:48.32 SWS - - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
09:05:55.17 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:06:07.81 SWS - - - - Idling
09:11:04.97 USH - - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
09:11:07.42 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
09:11:47.20 USH - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
09:11:50.56 USH - - - - Idling
09:55:05.32 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:55:05.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:55:05.32 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:55:32.40 --- - - - - *** sws to aft for
09:55:33.87 SWS - - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
09:55:46.36 --- - - - - *** pirouette manoeuvre
09:55:52.97 --- - - - - *** on ground
09:56:43.75 --- - - - - *** sws zenith during pirouette 0 degrees
09:57:42.69 --- - - - - *** end pirouette
09:58:01.35 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:01.46 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:01.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:05.69 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:06.99 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:09.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:09.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:13.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:17.03 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:58:23.40 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:28.84 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:30.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:30.97 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:31.18 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:58:34.88 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:36.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:39.10 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:58:51.70 --- - - - - *** take off roll
09:59:05.81 --- - - - - *** sws 90 deg aft
09:59:34.00 --- - - - - *** airborne
09:59:56.69 --- - - - - *** start P1
10:00:06.95 USH - - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:00:09.80 USH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.

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10:00:17.10	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:00:20.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:20.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:21.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:25.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:25.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:28.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:27.38	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:01:45.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 10F
10:03:54.82	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:03:58.04	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
10:04:01.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:04.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:18.51	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:05:21.11	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
10:05:22.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:05:24.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:05:39.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** little bit cloud above
10:12:08.15	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 250ms.
10:12:13.05	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
10:12:17.75	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
10:12:22.53	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:12:27.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:35.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:47.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 8F
10:20:34.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** splodges of cloud above
10:21:01.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** AC at FL180
10:23:31.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P1 and Start R1 at FL220
10:23:57.38	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:24:04.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
10:24:08.02	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
10:24:13.95	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
10:24:18.31	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
10:24:22.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:25.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:30.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:30.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:30.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:33.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:35.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:38.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:41.79	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:34:58.52	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
10:35:02.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:35:10.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:23.54	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:41:28.73	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
10:41:32.33	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:41:34.84	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
10:41:39.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
10:41:41.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:49.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:59.29	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:43:03.14	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
10:43:05.77	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
10:43:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
10:43:17.45	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
10:43:19.68	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
10:43:21.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:24.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:50.02	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
10:53:55.11	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
10:53:59.34	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
10:54:02.67	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
10:54:07.08	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
10:54:09.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:17.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:22.73	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
10:55:34.54	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
10:55:37.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:55:40.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:36.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:37.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:37.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:13:40.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:41.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:13:44.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:15:14.48	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
11:15:16.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:20.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:32:46.18	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
11:32:51.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:32:59.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:02.44	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
11:35:06.41	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
11:35:09.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:09.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:10.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:35:12.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:13.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:18.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:59:12.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end R1
11:59:32.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** starting descent
12:03:12.65	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
12:03:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:17.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:17.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:21.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:21.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:25.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:43.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 176R during descent
12:10:33.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** small cu below
12:10:59.91	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
12:11:04.04	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
12:11:06.80	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:11:10.32	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:11:12.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:11:13.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:11:16.69	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:12:14.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 3 F during descent
12:16:19.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud tops 6500ft
12:17:41.71	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
12:17:46.02	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 250ms.
12:17:48.61	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
12:17:52.30	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
12:18:14.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:18:18.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:19:16.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** R2 startet 121731
12:22:00.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run start profile
12:22:09.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 7500ft
12:24:30.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** through cloud
12:25:51.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** out of cloud
12:26:04.71	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
12:26:09.20	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 50ms.
12:26:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
12:26:16.05	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
12:26:19.32	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
12:26:44.51	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
12:26:47.42	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
12:26:50.50	LSH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
12:26:55.05	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
12:27:08.73	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:27:13.98	USH	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
12:27:17.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:17.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:18.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:27:18.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:20.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:22.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:27:27.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** ready for orbits
12:28:12.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** start orbit1
12:28:19.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** 005degress
12:29:24.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** end
12:29:28.55	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
12:29:32.98	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
12:29:36.04	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:29:41.45	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
12:29:43.54	USH	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
12:29:45.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:45.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:45.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:47.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:49.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:49.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

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12:30:03.75 --- - - - - *** start orbit 2
12:30:10.88 --- - - - - *** 090 degrees
12:31:28.63 --- - - - - *** end
12:31:32.08 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 75ms.
12:31:35.06 SWS - - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:31:38.84 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
12:31:41.32 USH - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
12:31:44.98 LSH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
12:31:47.86 LSH - - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
12:31:49.31 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:31:49.42 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:31:49.60 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:31:51.15 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:31:53.97 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:31:54.76 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:31:57.19 --- - - - - *** start orbit 3
12:32:11.10 --- - - - - *** 160 degrees
12:33:21.96 --- - - - - *** end orbits
12:33:56.84 --- - - - - *** all orbits at 45Deg AOB right hand turns
12:34:18.05 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
12:34:21.08 SWS - - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:34:23.36 SWS - - 10 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
12:34:28.60 LSH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
12:34:40.77 USH - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:35:19.40 --- - - - - *** start profile ascent
12:39:32.00 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
12:39:36.36 SWS - - 10 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
12:39:40.66 SWS - - - - 75 NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
12:39:45.52 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:45.52 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:45.53 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:46.70 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:50.16 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:51.39 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:24.42 LSH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
12:42:27.38 LSH - - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
12:42:30.34 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:38.28 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:56.98 --- - - - - *** end profile climb and strt descent to fl120
12:46:34.41 --- - - - - *** end profile descent at FL120
12:46:41.77 --- - - - - *** Start run
12:46:55.94 --- - - - - *** R4.1
13:03:35.34 --- - - - - *** end R4.1 start P6
13:07:12.62 --- - - - - *** sws to 8F for climb
13:09:59.49 --- - - - - *** End profile 6 and start r5.1 at FL180
13:10:19.65 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
13:10:23.08 SWS - - 10 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
13:10:26.43 SWS - - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:10:30.64 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
13:10:34.38 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:10:34.40 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:10:35.11 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:10:36.01 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:10:38.82 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:10:43.04 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:11:51.35 --- - - - - *** end run start profile to fl160
13:13:41.31 SWS - - - - 75 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
13:13:46.63 LSH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
13:13:49.52 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:49.92 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:49.94 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:13:51.10 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:13:54.56 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:13:57.48 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:08.04 --- - - - - *** start R6.1 at FL160
13:23:41.67 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:23:42.01 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:23:42.16 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:23:42.89 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:23:46.87 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:23:49.07 SWS 6F - - - - - Telescope position set to 6F
13:23:50.16 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:14.24 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
13:27:17.50 SWS - - 10 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
13:27:20.66 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:21.85 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:29:18.00 SWS - - 20 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 20ms.

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13:29:21.97	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
13:29:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:25.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:05.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** end r6.1 and start P8 to FL220
13:33:28.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 8F for climb
13:33:40.94	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
13:33:45.24	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
13:33:49.91	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
13:33:53.18	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
13:33:55.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:33:57.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:03.93	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
13:34:07.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:15.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:55.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** end P8 and start R at FL220
13:37:11.70	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
13:37:22.05	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 100ms.
13:37:25.85	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
13:37:29.84	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
13:37:41.77	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
13:37:46.34	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
13:37:50.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:50.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:50.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:37:53.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:54.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:37:58.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:34.72	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
13:40:36.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:40.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:53.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run and start dscent
14:03:26.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 177 sft during descent
14:04:54.47	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
14:04:57.74	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
14:04:59.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:01.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:23.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** At FL150 and in light dust
14:09:50.60	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
14:10:20.48	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
14:10:25.78	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
14:10:30.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:30.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:30.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:10:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:34.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:38.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:17:15.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** over the sea
14:17:25.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** off the Mauritanian coast
14:18:13.64	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:18:23.01	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
14:18:29.34	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
14:18:34.28	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
14:18:39.27	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
14:18:43.23	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:18:48.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:48.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:48.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:53.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:56.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:56.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:18:58.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 2500ft
14:19:40.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** in a turn
14:21:34.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** still nadir
14:22:31.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile at 100ft. Start rune
14:22:49.28	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 20ms.
14:22:52.74	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 150ms.
14:22:57.44	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
14:23:01.00	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
14:23:05.01	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 20ms.
14:23:07.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:09.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:14.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:14.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:15.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:16.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:19.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:19.71	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.

14:23:22.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:23.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:24.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:03.86	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:30:19.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** and has been since 142231
14:30:31.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** not this
14:30:38.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** note this
14:30:46.04	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:30:49.35	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:33:02.53	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
14:33:10.53	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 10ms.
14:33:13.76	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
14:33:16.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:33:18.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:00.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end run 8.1
14:36:21.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science
14:36:32.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** data stop for landing

ARIES flight log

Flight: B296

page 1 of 4

Date: 21 Jun 07 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: NIAGARA TO NUSAKHOTI

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
08 57 42	on the pan.	1x60	CH	C	71	44	Script 1: (1x60 CDS, 1x60 HRS)
10:00 ~	TAKSOFF						
10 13 12	RI						
10 23 25	FL230?	1x60	CH	C	71	41	Script 1
10 24	"	360x1	N	C	71	41	Dusty below, clear above ^{surface visible} same river?
10 27 50	"	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 29 35		360x1	N	C	71	41	Acquisition rate very low - aborting
10 31 35		360x1	N	C	71	41	OK
10 34 39		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 35 57		360x1	N	C	71	41	Some dust below / patchy Ci above
10 39 03		1x60	CH	C	71	41	1038 Sonda
10 40 19		360x1	N	C	71	41	- Aborted for Z coinciding with stars
10 41		120x1	Z	⊙	70	40	- Aborted at 99% as acquisition seemed to stop.
10 43 09		120x1	N	C	71	42	Clear above
10 44 12		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 45 27		360x1	N	C	71	41	
10 48 32		1x60	CH	C	70	41	
10 49 48		360x1	N	C	71	41	V. Dusty below. Surface visible.
10 52 51		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 53 52		360 x1	Z	⊙	70	41	Shutter greying at start of view
10 54 49		240x1	N	C	71	41	Dust thickening below
10 56 50		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
10 58 11		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 01 17		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 02 32		360x1	N	C	71	41	V. dusty below, surface still visible
11 05 33		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 06 54		360x1	N	C	71	41	Dust thickening. Surface barely visible
11 09 57		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 10 39		360x1	N	C	71	40	Did I start this, or did it self abort?
11 11 41		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 14 44		1x60	CH	C	71	41	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B296

page 12 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
		360x1	N	C			
11:15	FL230 ⁷	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 17 07		360x1	N	C	71	41	V. dusty below. Surface barely visible.
11 20 11		1x60	CH	C	71	41	↳ Banking during view.
11 21 30		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 24 32		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 26 12		480x1	N	C			Lunch!
11 30 15		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 31 37		480x1	N	C	71	42	Surface barely visible.
11 35 39		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 37 01		480x1	N	C	71	41	Still v. dusty below, still eating lunch.
11 41 09		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 42 35		480x1	N	C	71	41	Surface obscured.
11 46 38		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 47 52		360x1	N	C	71	41	Surface obscured.
11 50 55		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
11 52 11		360x1	N	C	71	41	
11 55 14		1x60	CH	C	76	41	
11 56 33		240x1	N	C	71	41	Surface obscured.
11 58 36	EOA PL	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
	FL230						
12 17 36		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 18 49		360x1	Z	O	70	40	Opening at start
12 21 57		1x60	CH	C	71	42	Ops - no delay before cal.
12 23 09		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
	FL075						
12 26 13	R3.1	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
12 27 04	Orbit 1	120x1	Z	O	70	41	45° RV
	"	"	Z	O			Abort at end of run.
12 29 26	O2	1x60	CH	O	70	41	Abort
12 30		120x1	Z	O			

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13296

page 3 of 4

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
		120x1	Z	0	70	41	Aborted at end of orbit.
12 32 1	03	"	Z	0	70	41	
12 33		"	Z	0	71	41	Aborted at end of orbit.
12 33 47		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 34 50		1x60	CH	C	71	42	Possibly interrupted at end.
12 36 28		1x60	CH	C	71	42	
12 46 42		1x60	CH	C			
12 47 55		360x1	Z	0	70	41	Dust above
12 51 07		120x1	N	C	70	41	Dust & broken cloud below.
5							→ Software lock up.
12 58 04	FL ¹²⁰ 120	1x60	CH	C	71	41	← RESTART SOFTWARE
12 59 34		360x1	N				Aborted - looking wrong way!
13 00 06		240x1	Z	0	70	41	Shutter opening during last 15% or so.
13 02 34		120x1	N	C	71	42	Aborted at end of run.
13 03 14	P6↑	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 09 35		1x60	CH	C			
13 10 20		120x1	Z	0	71	41	Z Shutter opening at start ???
13 11 21			N	C			V. thick dust below.
13 11 50	PJ	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 12 35		"	CH	C	71	41	
#							
13 13 51	FL160	1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 15 12		240x1	Z	0	70	41	In thick dust
13 17:40		240x1	N	C	71	41	Thick dust below. Surface features visible below
13 19 26		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 20 43		240x1	Z	0	71	42	
13 22 54		240x1	N	C	71	41	
13 24 59		1x60	CH	C	71	41	
13 32 12		1x60	CH	C	71	41	In climb? ✓
13 33 30		360x1	N	C	71	41	Thick dust below / clear above / surface obscured.
13 36 40	FL220	1x60	CH	C	71	41	

Flight:

B296

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:47:35

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

ADA:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:49:08

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B296

Date: 21 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. pcasp motor failed

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Flight B296 10:19:34

Heading 310 deg Speed 265 knots Height 18.5kft Press 495mb

Lat 14°24.0'N Long 1°12.0'E Wind 9 ms-1/ 99 deg

Temp -8.26C Dewpoint -11.49C

From 10:01:29 to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	18.52	Kft
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	62.35	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	146.35	ppb
----	TECO SO2	0.14	ppb
----	TECO NO2	-0.22	ppb

● All
○
○
○
○

New plot, same times

Flight B296 10:00:48

Heading 268 deg Speed 221 knots Height 1.6kft Press 955mb

Lat 13°24.0'N Long 2°6.0'E Wind 5 ms-1/ 225 deg

Temp 29.7C Dewpoint 21.12C

From 09:51:50 to now

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	36048	secs
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	901.39	W m-2
—	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	429.38	W m-2
—	SOLAR ZENITH ANGLE	28.49	deg
—	SOLAR AZIMUTH ANGLE	65.43	deg

New plot, same times

Flight B296 10:00:21

Heading 268 deg Speed 203 knots Height 1.2kft Press 969mb

Lat 13°24.0'N Long 2°6.0'E Wind 4 ms-1/ 263 deg

Temp 30.17C Dewpoint 21.15C

From 09:51:50 to now

Current values

---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	36021	secs	☒ All
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	886.17	W m-2	☐
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	423.48	W m-2	☐
---	SOLAR ZENITH ANGLE	28.87	deg	☐
---	SOLAR AZIMUTH ANGLE	65.65	deg	☐

B296 Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

EAA051_20070621_0915.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 0915 UTC

EAA041_20070621_0915.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 0915 UTC

EAA051_20070621_1030.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 1030 UTC

EAA041_20070621_1030.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 1030 UTC

EAA051_20070621_1100.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 1100 UTC

EAA041_20070621_1100.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 1100 UTC

EAA051_20070621_1115.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 1115 UTC

EAA041_20070621_1115.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 1115 UTC

EAA051_20070621_1245.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 1245 UTC

EAA041_20070621_1245.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 1245 UTC

EAA051_20070621_1330.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 21 Jun 2007 1330 UTC

EAA041_20070621_1330.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 21 Jun 2007 1330 UTC

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B296:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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